

EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATIVE MEANING THROUGH METAPHORS IN RAUF PARFI'S POETRY

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Abstract. *In this article, connotative meanings of word used in Rauf Parfi's poetry will be presented briefly. The way connotative words are represented with lexic methods in the poet's poetry will be dealt with in terms of the author's poems.*

Key words: *connotative, denotative, phonetic, lexic method, metaphore, morning, leaf, simile.*

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ КОННОТАТИВНОГО СМЫСЛА ЧЕРЕЗ МЕТАФОРЫ В ПОЭЗИИ РАУФА ПАРФИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье кратко описаны коннотативные значения лексических единиц, используемых в поэзии Рауфа Парфи. На примере стихотворений поэта исследуется выражение коннотативного значения в стихотворениях поэта лексическими методами.*

Ключевые слова: *коннотативный, денотативный, фонетический, лексический прием, метафорический перенос значения, заря, лист, сравнение.*

Rauf Parfi is a fiery poet who has earned his rightful place in the Uzbek literature of the 20th century with his unique poems. The work of the poet is distinguished from other poets by the fact that he creates unique metaphors, skillfully uses words that do not repeat one another. There are many metaphors in Rauf Parfi's poetry. This is one of the main tools that ensure the individuality of the poet's work. Asqad Mukhtar admitted: "Rauf Parfi chose the method of complex and dynamic metaphors in poetry. In it, not only some images, but the entire poem is built on the movement of metaphor, the metaphor turns into poetic language, the logic of the image, the richness of poetic thinking. In Rauf Parfi's poems, there are many words, wind, rain, leaf, frost, night, day, moon, mountain... As the poet's work improved, the weight of these images increased, and the words that were once used in their own sense later took on the color of a perfect image. So, these are metaphors, a way of transferring word meanings.

Metaphor (Gr. metaphora - transfer) is the use of a lexeme to express another meaning based on external, apparent similarity.

Metaphorical meaning occurs in the following cases:

one word is better suited to the speaker's purpose of expression than the other, and therefore the second is used instead of the first;

there is no representative of a denotation, and a certain word is used to represent another denotation.

Therefore, artistic language tools such as simile and metaphor are important in the work of the poet. Rauf Parfi's poetry encourages us to reflect on the poet's literary heritage, beautiful poems, and the use of similes that do not repeat each other. For example:

The morning is breaking, the morning is shooting arrows,
It's dawn, the sun is shining.

The wounded globe lies,
Green belt on the head.
("Dawn is breaking")

The poet's hopes and bright feelings are expressed in the poem "Dawn is breaking". In this poem, the sun is compared to a cannon, and its golden rays are compared to arrows. The sun continuously rains arrows. This analogy is not for nothing, in fact, the propagation of light in the form of particles is a physical law. In this poem, the poet has created a wonderful metaphor. The globe looks as if those particles have been wounded by bullets. This situation has moved from a natural phenomenon to humans. Every day, a person who wakes up in the morning is greeted with a clear, beautiful morning. The purity of the morning moves to people's hearts. The priority of images related to mother nature and nature as the main sources of metaphors used in Rauf Parfi's work determines the uniqueness of imagery in the poet's work. Beautiful examples of metaphors can be found in all the poems of the poet. This is the unique style of the poet. It is difficult to understand the work of Rauf Parfi from one reading. Every time you read it, you can see the subtle aspects of his work. His collection "Sokina" contains such a poem:

A ghazal written on the waves of the river,
The grass is bending over and reading a book.
A moment of joy and laughter,
The sun will sigh for a moment.
(Rauf Parfi 1964)

We can see a beautiful example of metaphor in such units as Maysa bending over to read a book and the sun sighing. He moved the position of reading a book while bending over to the lawns. But in nature, it is possible to observe the condition of the grass facing the ground. By copying the situation of a person's sighing from something to the sun, the sun sighs and expresses a sad state. One of the bright aspects of the artist's artistic skill that distinguishes him from others is the uniqueness of his language.

The expression of the metaphorical meaning in the text is inextricably linked with the inner goal of the speaker and increases the impact of the thought. It appears as the starting point of influencing the listener's feelings and creating a new speech situation.

A metaphor is an inanimate thing - creating a beautiful simile by transferring human characteristics to events. In Rauf Parfi's poems such as "Trouble", "Night thinks", "My heart has become thin", "Dawn is breaking", "Summer night" and "Yomg 'ir yog'ar" he draws beautiful examples through metaphors. The poet connected the spring, autumn, and summer seasons with the fact that he refers to nature more in the expression of his emotional experiences, and brought that state into the human psyche. He created beautiful poems by transcribing natural phenomena that occur in the summer season.

As a result, he tries to illuminate their expression scheme through the use of metaphors in his poetry. Professors H. Nematov and R. Rasulov divide the components of a seme into names (denotative), expression and task semes. Among these schemas, the schema of expression is the object of research for pragmatics. Therefore, we can see that in the metaphorical units used by Rauf Parfi, connotative symbols are formed in a unique way along with the fire symbol. Because the poet managed to create individual types of metaphors that are not found in Uzbek linguistics.

That is why, if we analyze the poet's poetry in depth, we will see that he has created new metaphors belonging to his pen. This requires a deeper study of the poet's poetry.

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